

PERSONALITY IN COMMUNITY ECOLOGY RESPONSES: INTEGRATING THE BEHAVIOUR AND INTERACTIONS OF A MARINE INVADER — PINCER

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Template: European Commission (Horizon 2020)

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Grant number: 836937

Project abstract:

Consistent behavioural variation between individuals of the same species (i.e. animal personality) is very common in animals, from mammals to fish and insects. Personality types like boldness/shyness can change how the individual interacts with its environment, e.g. the outcome of predator-prey interactions. However, the effects of widespread personality variability on ecosystems is relatively unexplored. Recent work shows that personality variability can alter the nature of trophic interactions between species and potentially contribute to ecosystem stability. Therefore, PinCER will investigate animal personality as a functional trait, quantifying links between personality (e.g. boldness, exploration etc.) and diet, trophic position and body condition in individual animals. By quantifying the degree that personality variability translates to functional diversity in food webs, PinCER will provide unprecedented insights into the effects of personality on ecosystems. Building on the experimental work, a review paper will also investigate existing empirical literature on behavioural variability's role in species interactions. Experimental work will focus on the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*), analysing the links between personality and trophic interactions across an ecological invasion gradient. The round goby is an invasive fish in the Baltic Sea and European inlet waters and a proven study subject for behavioural research. Results will also have management implications, giving highly focused individual data on the species' impacts on Baltic Sea communities. A full-time secondment in the Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (Helsinki Commission) will focus on invasive species policy (management of ship-mediated introductions of non-indigenous species, e.g. the round goby) enhancing my training and career prospects. As such, PinCER will advance behavioural and community ecology, meet my skill acquisition needs and produce data for ecosystem management.

Last modified: 03-02-2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement - No 836937

PERSONALITY IN COMMUNITY ECOLOGY RESPONSES: INTEGRATING THE BEHAVIOUR AND INTERACTIONS OF A MARINE INVADER — PINCER - UPDATED DMP

DMP PHILOSOPHY

PinCER defines “data” in the context of the MSCA-IF, Contract as “all digital outputs that are direct products of the research action”. As such, we aim for a Digital Output Management Plan that applies FAIR Principles outlined below to all PinCER digital outputs.

The PinCER digital outputs will all be centralized in DOI-issued digital storage repositories (Open Science Framework project, 'OSF', osf.io/rnz7q/), to provide long-term, searchable, and accessible data storage.

The initial project DMP will be updated at PinCER 12-month and 24-month milestones (Jan 12 2021, Jan 12 2022), to implement this philosophy to outputs beyond just experimental and field data.

1. DATA SUMMARY

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Data is generated in two experimental work packages (WP1, WP2 in the project proposal, hereafter '*experimental data*'), and in the meta-analysis work package (WP3, hereafter '*meta-analysis data*').

These three work packages are each designed as independent empirical studies to test specific research hypotheses; therefore, the primary use and purpose of data collection will be for input into data analysis for hypothesis testing.

As of Jan 2021, *experimental data* collection for WP1 and *meta-analysis data* collection for WP3 are both ongoing, and WP2 *experimental data* collection is due to begin in April - May 2021.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Experimental data collected, their form and format are as follow:

1. Data collection from fieldwork/sampling includes water quality parameters, GPS locations of sampling sites, sample numbers/fish-counts etc.. are collected by directly by researchers (specific measurement equipment is to be determined based on availability). The format of data from fieldwork is initially recorded by hand in datasheets in teams of two (one person measuring, one recording). This physical data, is then entered in excel (.xlsx) spreadsheets.
2. Physical samples are collected of animal and plant tissue. Physical tissue are held frozen in the laboratory for use of stable isotope analysis of tissue and quantitative gut content analysis. As the planned analysis for these samples largely consumes the samples, any remnants of the samples following analysis are not held for long-term storage after use.

3. Physical journals for animal experiments are maintained in accordance with Danish animal ethics regulations (Bekendtgørelse om dyreforsøg, Kapitel 4). This contemporaneously records the details of animal experiments at each step, e.g. collection and transport of animals, when and which experiments are used on animals, etc.
4. All other data is collected digitally in the laboratory, including video analysis of behaviour, behavioural variables from video processing, stable isotope abundances, and quantitative gut content analysis. The format of experimental data collected digitally within the laboratory will be collected and stored in the following formats:

Experimental Digital Data	Collection Method	Format
Video data of behavioural experiments	Recording using Logitech Brio, and Logitech Capture software	stored as .mp4
Video processing data	Collected via non-proprietary software (e.g. ToxTrac, doi: 10.1111/2041-210X.12874)	.tox files and their associated data, with data output to .csv
Stable isotope data	Analysed externally (via the UEA Stable Isotope Platform https://www.uea.ac.uk/about/faculties-and-schools/faculty-of-science/facilities/stable-isotope-platform)	excel and .csv files
Gut content data	Not currently being collected	excel and .csv files
Data analysis code and outputs	Data will be processed and analyzed using the open access R Statistical Program	.csv files (data output) .R files (code) .Rdata files (statistical models)

Meta-analysis data is entirely digital, as extracted from online databases (e.g. Web of Science, Scopus), extracted data from published papers or publish datasets from supplementary information and public repositories (e.g. datadryad.org, osf.io), and received from direct correspondence with third parties.

The main types and format of meta-analysis data are as follows:

Meta-Analytic Digital Data	Format
Bibliographic data extracted from online scientific databases	Cross compatible bibliographic formations (e.g. .bib, .bibx), with associated published papers stored as PDFs
Systematic review screening and processing databases (e.g. to record my inclusion and exclusion reasons in the title/abstract screening process)	excel and .csv files
Data extracted by myself from reading and compiling data from published papers and public repositories	excel and .csv files
Third party datasets obtained from public repositories or received through correspondence	excel and .csv files data will also be stored in the original format that the data was received in
Data analysis code and outputs via the open access R Statistical Program	.csv files (data output) .R files (code) .Rdata files (statistical models)

Output formats are all non-proprietary and compatible with open access data analysis software.

All data collection described above is quantitative, although qualitative data is also be collected at all stages as notes annotating both physical datasheets and digital data files.

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Experimental data is original. Re-use of existing datasets for experimental data is not currently planned.

Meta-analysis data inputs are entirely from reuse of published and unpublished third party datasets, but the data outputs from processing and modelling of this collected can be considered an original product of this project.

What is the origin of the data?

Experimental data is obtained by independent sampling and laboratory experiments conducted by myself. Stable isotope data is obtained via a third party, as this must be processed at an external stable isotope analysis laboratory (e.g. via the UEA Stable Isotope Platform <https://www.uea.ac.uk/about/faculties-and-schools/faculty-of-science/facilities/stable-isotope-platform>).

Meta-analysis data is obtained by conducting a systematic review of published literature, extracted from scientific databases. Additional data is obtained from contacting authors, where their published data is insufficiently complete to be included in our analyses.

What is the expected size of the data?

Experimental data is approximately 100-150GB across the two experimental work packages. This will primarily be due to the 20-50 video files per experiment of up to 1GB each.

(NOTE: This has been revised down from initial estimates, as the number of videos are below what was expected)

Meta-analysis data is approximately 3-5 GB per study. The largest components of this are expected to be PDF copies of published papers, and the output .Rdata models from data analysis.

(NOTE: 3-4 meta-analysis systematic review papers are expected to be produced linked to this project, so the estimate has been revised to be 'per study'. Nonetheless, the total is still low)

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

The two primary groups that may be able to re-use data from this project are: 1) research and academic audiences with an interest in behavioural ecology, invasive species ecology, or the round goby as a specific study species; and 2) Decision makers in environmental management and policy. Relevant decision making bodies include those with a focus on the Baltic Sea ecosystems, such as the Working Group on Introductions and Transfers of Marine Organisms for the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea 'ICES', and the Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission - Helsinki Commission (HELCOM).

2.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

Upon publication, all data that contributes to the analysis and conclusions of a publication will primarily be made publicly available via project within Open Science Framework (OSF) (osf.io/ztdcx) and GitHub/Zenodo (zenodo.org/communities/pincer/).

It is expected that 3 - 4 separate OSF project repositories will be established by the end of the project, one for each planned publication. OSF projects allocate DOIs to each project.

Data analysis will be conducted within the R Statistical Program using GitHub as version control. Github allows integration with OSF projects, such that all scripts /code for analysis as well as input and output data from analysis

will be publically available through OSF. All analysis code will be annotated with the intention of making it understandable by academic peers.

Upon publication of output datasets, data held in GitHub will also be archived on the Zenodo PinCER Collection to preserve a long-term time-stamped version-controlled copy of the digital analysis output and datasets associated with the publication

See for example the following public data for the study: "Poor nutritional condition promotes high-risk behaviours: A systematic review and meta-analysis"

OSF database: <https://osf.io/3tphj/> (10.17605/OSF.IO/3TPHJ)

GitHub repository: https://github.com/NPMoran/metah06_condition-dependence-of-boldness OSF

Zenodo data record: <https://zenodo.org/record/4497526> (10.5281/zenodo.4497526)

NOTE: For collaboration on studies lead by external authors, data management and storage is controlled by the external authors and are outside of the scope this DMP. Were applicable, our aim is for those studies to meet the same reporting standards as described here (See for example: 'Materials for "Illustrating the importance of meta-analysing variances alongside means in ecology and evolution"' <https://osf.io/yjua8/>)

What naming conventions do you follow?

Quantitative datasets will be uploaded with metadata files. This will include descriptors for all variables used, based on standard terminological conventions used in behavioural ecology and food-web ecology, as well as any contextual data that is essential understanding the dataset, such as the time and date of experiments used, ID of observers etc. There are no specific applicable naming conventions.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Keyword searchability is incorporated within data storage processes (Zenodo, OSF), described above. Both include a Tags or Keywords section for searchable keywords and a 'Wiki' section for a detailed description of the project's purpose and contents. Therefore, all datasets that form part of these projects will be readily discoverable.

Do you provide clear version numbers?

This is done automatically within the data storage processes (Zenodo, OSF) described above.

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

This is done automatically within the data storage processes (Zenodo, OSF) described above.

2.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

Data related to publications and the analysis and conclusions therein will be publically available following publication, via a public OSF and Github/Zenodo repositories (See section 2.1 above).

Data from WP1-WP3 may be kept private prior to publication (by setting the OSF project Repository to private) in the case that it will form a significant contribution to a future planned project/publication and publishing it would jeopardize the publication of that future project.

Some project data will not be uploaded to these open OSF project repositories where it is not practical, specifically hard copies of data sheets, original video files of behavioural experiments, although these will be maintained for a minimum period (5 years from project completion or publication of research, whichever is later) and may be accessed on reasonable request.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

See section 2.1 above

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

All data will be stored in formats based on non-proprietary software formats (see descriptions in section 1.1 above), so all data will be widely accessible. This includes: widely cross compatible .csv files for quantitative databases; .bib bibliographic files usable with open access bibliographic software Zotero; and .R and .Rdata files for use with the open access R Statistical Program).

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No applicable

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No applicable

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

See section 2.1 above

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Not applicable

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

Through both OSF and Zenodo, all outputs will then be broadly findable and usable by target audiences using a standard open license for use (e.g. License: CC-By Attribution 4.0 International).

Is there a need for a data access committee?

Not applicable

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?

Published datasets and databases will be appropriately licensed (e.g. License: CC-By Attribution 4.0 International).

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Not applicable

2.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Quantitative datasets will be uploaded to OSF and Github/Zenodo with metadata files. This will include descriptors for all variables used, based on standard terminological conventions used in behavioural ecology and food-web ecology, as well as any contextual data that is essential understanding the dataset, such as the time and date of experiments used, ID of observers etc. I expect that all variables and contextual information will be able to be described in plain English, so that all data will be semantically interoperable.

It is expected that all data will also have broad technical interoperability, as it will be recorded in widely used file formats compatible with open access software. This includes: widely cross compatible .csv files for quantitative databases; .bib bibliographic files usable with open access bibliographic software Zotero; and .R and .Rdata files for use with the open access R Statistical Program).

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

See above.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

See above.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Not applicable.

2.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENCES)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Data will be re-usable using standard licensing under the OSF framework. I intend to use licensing requiring acknowledgement and citation of the original source (e.g. License: CC-By Attribution 4.0 International).

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

It is expected that data will be made available at the point of publication (see for example <https://osf.io/3tphj/>), although data will also be available earlier in cases where a manuscript is submitted to a preprint server prior to publication (e.g. see for example <https://ecoevorxiv.org/sbrvu/>).

Data from a project may be kept private for a limited period of time (by setting an OSF project Repository to private), only where it forms a significant contribution to another planned project/publication and publishing it would jeopardize the publication of that future project.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Data reuse is available under the appropriate licence. (e.g. License: CC-By Attribution 4.0 International)

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Data will remain on OSF and Zenodo repositories indefinitely.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Not applicable.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

There is no cost for data preservation on publically available servers, while maintenance of personal cloud storage is covered by the researcher (\$11.99AUD/ month). The time costs to the researcher of have been taken into account when planning the person-hours allocated to the project work packages.

There are no additional costs to DTU for the long-term preservation of the digital data on departmental servers and physical data in storage at DTU. Data will be stored for a minimum of 5 years following project completion or the final publication originating from this project (whichever is longer).

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

The is not expected to be any specific costs allocated to the Horizon 2020 grant. The only notable costs is the maintenance of personal cloud storage is covered by the researcher (\$11.99AUD/ month).

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

As the primary researcher, I (Nicholas Moran) am responsible for data management, curation and preservation of data during the life of the project (2 year). Following completion of the project I will remain responsible for long-term preservation of all published data stored in repositories (OSF, GitHub/Zenodo), and keep a copy of all project data personal cloud storage (www.dropbox.com). The supervisors (Prof. Andre Visser and Dr Jane Behrens) will be responsible for long-term preservation of the DTU departmental copy of all digital data on DTU servers, as well as all remaining physical data at DTU Aqua, Lyngby.

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

Data preservation issues have been discussed and there are not outstanding issues.

4. DATA SECURITY

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

To ensure data is recoverable, copies of all digital data will be held on DTU departmental servers and on the researcher's personal cloud (Dropbox). Departmental servers will only be accessible to relevant DTU staff (which will only include myself, and after the end of the project the supervisors, Prof. Andre Visser and Dr Jane Behrens). Data on the personal Dropbox is only accessible to the Nicholas Moran.

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

See above (section 2.1)

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

This project involves the use of live animals, and relevant approvals for the experimentation on animals have been obtained (see PinCER project Deliverable D1.1). A physical journal for animal experiments will be maintained in accordance with Danish animal ethics regulations (Bekendtgørelse om dyreforsøg, Kapitel 4). This will contemporaneously record the details of animal experiments at each step, e.g. collection and transport of animals, when and which experiments are used on animals, etc. This journal will be stored along with all physical experimental data from this project, and maintained of a minimum of five years from the completion of animal experiments as required by regulations).

Data will not contain any personal or confidential information. Although, meta-analysis data will include records of correspondence with academics regarding their publications and the data therein. Although we do not consider this correspondence strictly confidential, we will treat this correspondence as private and sensitive in nature. Therefore, this data will be stored securely with other digital data, but redacted from datasets uploaded to public repositories. In addition, any primary datasets received from academics via correspondence will be redacted from published datasets.

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Not applicable

6. OTHER ISSUES

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

This data management plan follows and has been drafted in line with:

1. Research Data Procedure and Guidelines - DTU Aqua
2. DTU Policy of the Retention of Primary Material and Data
3. DTU Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
4. DTU Information Security Policy
5. Guidelines to rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications & Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020
6. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020